

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF USING TESTS FOR ASSESSING THEIR MOTOR SKILLS IN THE SELECTION OF YOUNG FOOTBALL PLAYERS

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Annotation: the article discusses in detail the issues of selection in a football sport and the test tests used in selection. Based on the opinions of scientists who studied the problems of selection and selection of young players, topical issues of assessing their speed and endurance skills were studied and analyzed.

Keywords: selection, objective assessment, motor skills, speed, endurance, sports achievements, key factors, physiological factors, achievement, reliability of tests.

In our country, special attention is paid to setting priorities aimed at attracting the population to mass sports, gaining skills and knowledge in the field of physical education and sports, introducing innovative forms and methods into the process of selection (selection) of talented athletes. "Measures to take the development of football in Uzbekistan to a completely new level" of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, covering current issues in football, such as turning football into the most popular sport among the population, selecting young players with high talent on" of the decree No. PD 5387, section 1, paragraph 1, to increase the interest of children and teenagers in playing football, popularize amateur football, in this regard, comprehensive schools, other educational institutions, neighborhood and Organizations pay special attention to regular organization of football competitions.

The active development and search for objective methods of selection and selection began mainly in the 90s. "Sprint versus endurance" test allows to determine motor skills - endurance and speed. This test is widely used in Germany, Israel and other European countries.

Speed plays an important role in the selection and selection of young players. In this test, speed abilities can be determined with an error of 2-3% from the total number of test takers. If we pay attention to the game of Ronaldo and Messi, we can talk about their high coordination, sense of rhythm and quickness of their movements. In Spain, these qualities are evaluated using special tests. Professor Stula (Poland) tried to develop a test designed to evaluate rhythmic coordination and high frequency of foot movements in football players.

At the 2014 FIFA World Cup in Brazil, forwards from top teams demonstrated high-speed running skills in finishing attacking moves, where forwards outpaced defenders, highly technical demonstrated skills and achieved results in goal kicks from different distances up to 25-30 m.

The best strikers of the championship D. Rodriguez (Colombia), T. Muller (Germany), L. Messi (Argentina), A. Robben (Netherlands) demonstrated such skills. X. Diaz (Costa Rica), S. Airer (Côte D'Ivoire), G. Higuain (Argentina), A. Pereira (Uruguay) were the fastest running forwards. The running speed of these players is 34 km/h. Converting to a typical value, this is 9.4 m/s or 10.5-10.6 s per 100 m. It is known that sprinters of the international class reach an

average speed of more than 10 m/s. It can be said that the above-mentioned players also reached a speed of 10 m/s in short sections of the football field from 10 m to 30 m in some game episodes. These facts once again confirm the modern trends in conditioning and technical training of elite football players from the stage of initial sports training.

Most experts dealing with the problem of selecting football players talk about the need to use all possible methods to identify the motor frontal pathways, on which sports achievements in this sport depend. At this point, it is primarily about speed and coordination. These predispositions are strongly conditioned by genotype factors and are less influenced by training. Among them, the structure of muscle fibers is of great importance. In all human skeletal muscles, the percentage of "fast" and "slow" fibers is not the same. They have muscles with a large number of slow-twitch fibers (ST); in other muscles, fast fibers (FT) are dominant. In general, most muscles contain about 50% ST-type fibers and the same number of FT-type fibers, of which 25% are considered to be FTa and the rest FTb. These figures should be considered very approximate, because the amount of the above-mentioned types of muscle fibers is very different. In addition, in children who have not yet exercised, the usual percentage of fibers of the FTa type is considered to be higher than in adults (2-3%) (about 13% of the total muscle mass). This testifies, on the one hand, that children have a large reserve for future specialized training, and on the other hand, it indicates the validity of using the below test in selection and selection.

If we take into account the structure of the player's movement activity, individuals with a predominance of fast muscle fibers are more suitable for this game. Fast muscle fibers are divided into FTa and FTb. Metabolism of FTb fibers is mainly based on glycolytic processes; hence their other name: FG (Fast Glycolytic fibers or white fibers). They are characterized by a larger number of myofibrils than ST-type fibers. FT fibers are characterized by less aerobic endurance than FTa and ST fibers; however, they have a much higher anaerobic endurance. This is caused by a higher activity of metabolic processes (without the participation of oxygen) and is determined by a lower amount of myoglobin. These fibers are surrounded by fewer blood-carrying capillaries and have fewer mitochondria than ST-type fibers. Fibers are supplied with blood along small motoneurons. They have the ability to react to high-frequency impulses. In such fibers, the increase in tension occurs due to an increase in the frequency of stimulation, but in ST fibers, the increase in tension occurs due to the addition of additional motor units. Research shows that these fibers are not easily recruited by the nervous system, resulting in their low activity during low-intensity daily movement activity. At the same time, during high-intensity short-term exertion, for example, when running 100 m or swimming 50 m, they immediately start working. FTa fibers are activated during daily movement activity or during non-maximum-intensity, relatively long-lasting sports activities, such as running 1500 m or swimming 400 m, which are metabolically located between ST and FTb muscle fibers. . These fibers require both oxygen sources and non-oxygen sources to function. This is reflected in their name - FOG (Fast Oxidative Glycolytic - fast, oxygen-glycolytic fibers). Muscles dominated by fast fibers are characterized by low resistance to fatigue, high level of force generation and short time.

Slow fibers (ST). They are characterized by a large number of mitochondria, a large number of capillaries and more than 50% activity of enzymes that ensure the transport of oxygen. In humans, these fibers are characterized by the highest metabolism, which takes place with the participation of oxygen. They are otherwise called SO (Slow Oxidative - "free oxygen" or red

fibers due to the fact that they have a much larger amount of myoglobin than GT fibers). In addition, these fibers are very efficient in the production of ATR (adenosine triphosphate), an energy component necessary for muscle contraction. These carbohydrates are primarily associated with high energy efficiency of the oxidation reaction of fats, which accumulate energy for work. This allows you to maintain low or moderate intensity activity for a relatively long time. ST fibers are innervated by long motoneurons excited by low-frequency impulses of the low excitability threshold of the spinal cord, so they have a contraction time that is almost twice as long as G'T fibers (80 around m/sec). Muscles with a predominance of slow-twitch fibers are characterized by a high resistance to fatigue, generating force much more slowly and at a much lower rate than typical of GT-type fibers.

The results of studies on the percentage and participation of muscle fibers indicate that athletes with a large number of slow-twitch fibers in the working muscles achieve the best results in the direction of "endurance", while athletes with a predominance of fast-twitch fibers are shorter than humans. will have more options in the direction of "speed" which requires long and very intense forces, and today's football demands more of that. In the training system of modern football players, it is possible to estimate the structure of muscle fibers in children using a simple "sprint versus endurance" test. Depending on the percentage of FT and ST fibers, an individual may be predisposed to performing sprinting tasks (when GT fibers predominate) or predisposed to performing tasks associated with endurance performance (deposits) can have (when there are more ST-type fibers in it). Experts in the field of football recommend taking into account the following:

- the existence of a strong correlation between the speed of sprinting and the percentage of fibers of the GT type,
- the presence of a negative relationship between the percentage of GT-type fibers and the speed of long-distance running,
- the presence of a high correlation between the maximum consumption of oxygen and the percentage of ST-type fibers.

Evaluation of the effectiveness of the "Sprint versus endurance" test in the selection of boys for football training was carried out during the research, in which 12-13-year-old boys from the main schools of Opole and Sidezia voivodships participated. The number of people studied was 836, their average age was 11.5 years, body length - 154.9 cm, weight 47.9 kg. The research was conducted in April-May 2012. For comparison, the results of a study conducted in Szczecin in 2005, in which 120 12-13-year-old boys took part, were taken. Their biometric data: average age - 12 years and 5 months, body length - 159.0 cm, weight - 58.0 kg. All test subjects did not regularly engage in sports before the beginning of the research.

"Sprint versus endurance" style has more fast-twitch muscle fibers (TMT) and thus has an innate preference for short-term and intense exertion, and slow-twitch (ST) predominance. - allows to indirectly identify individuals with innate predispositions to long-term low-intensity stress. The test used for these purposes consisted of two running tasks - a 60 m run and a 12-minute run (Cooper's test). On the basis of the obtained results, the average arithmetic indicators and standard deviations of speed in running these two distances were calculated. This made it possible to construct a special table. According to the recommendations of the authors of the test, individuals with a high percentage of GT-type fibers should be characterized by very good results in sprinting and, at the same time, should have low results in long-distance running. In a study of 11-year-old boys, the presence of speed bumps was

found in 16 individuals, which is 1.91% of all studied. These are kids who have an innate aptitude for playing soccer and other sports where speed skills are key. A rather large number of those studied (3.82%, 32 children) have innate preferences for sports that require endurance. However, at the same time, the percentage of children with innate predispositions is considered too small for this method to be widespread in determining motor potential and thus in the selection and selection of children and young people for high-performance sports. One of the reasons for the very low results in both the speed test and the endurance test is the low effectiveness of the "physiological movement stimulus" effect in physical education classes, as well as the low motor activity of students in these classes, who in these classes have the entire duration of the class. only 12-28% is in motion. Such exercises do not lead to the development of adaptive mechanisms, at the same time, they do not involve the relevant genes and thus do not lead to the development of muscle fibers according to the stress. Among the studied boys, there were children who showed high results in both tests ("speed" and "endurance"). Among all studied, there were 64 such children, which is 7.7%.

Soccer experts base these numbers on skeletal muscle enzyme activity measurements—molecular studies more relevant to sprinting. In addition, it is necessary to pay attention to the fact that 11-year-old boys can observe accelerated physical development (acceleration) compared to their calendar age.

The results of a study conducted five years ago with 120 boys can testify to the usefulness of using the "sprint versus endurance" test in sports practice. Children with innate speed limits determined based on the presented method were admitted to football training despite their relatively high age (12 years) after passing an additional test for "coordination". It can be hoped that the 16 children with innate speed limits will later fall into the hands of professionals for training, and this was the practical task of the work. This also applies to children who have an innate aptitude for sports, for which endurance is one of the leading factors for achieving high results. In a study of 836 11-year-old boys, speed deficits were detected in 16 children, which is 1.91% of all children tested, and endurance deficits were detected in 32 subjects (3, 82 %). The number of identified individuals with high motor skills corresponds to the scientific data of a number of other authors.

The "sprint versus endurance" test used in research can be of practical importance in solving the problem of selection and selection of boys to play football and other types of sports. This can be confirmed by the fact of validly determining the speed of boys who have successfully continued their football career for 5 years.

Summary. A lot of research has been done on the selection and selection of young players, and all the researchers have mentioned the complexity of this topic as well as its urgency. The reliability of the tests used to evaluate them at different levels of readiness is very important. Many advanced scientists have emphasized the importance of the "Sprint versus endurance" test recommended by us in evaluating the motor skills of young football players. In the selection of young football players, the advantage of using tests for assessing motor skills rather than tests for assessing one or another physical quality has been proven.

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